

Translated from German to English (slightly shortened text):

Talk abstract "BIOPIGEE - Biosecurity practices for pig farming in Europe" at the conference of the Pig Health Service of North Rhine-Westphalia on 25 November 2021

Salmonella (SAL) and hepatitis E virus (HEV) are zoonotic pathogens that rarely cause clinical disease in pigs, but more frequently cause acute, chronic and sometimes fatal disease in humans. HEV infections in humans are considered an increasing problem in the EU. Pigs and food from pigs are regarded as a significant source of infection for humans. The aim of the BIOPIGEE project ("Biosecurity practices for pig farming across Europe" of the One Health European Joint Programme, Horizon 2020 of the EU, grant agreement no. 773830) is to identify effective and cost-efficient biosecurity measures to reduce the introduction and transmission of SAL and HEV along the pig production chain (husbandry, transport, slaughter) and thus contribute to the prevention of human infections. The project involves 19 partner institutes from 12 European countries.

In a literature study on effective biosecurity measures regarding SAL and HEV in primary production, 1643 articles from scientific journals were evaluated with the help of 10 reviewers from 7 partner institutes. The final selection included 26 articles on SAL and 4 on HEV. The most effective measures to reduce SAL transmission were identified as "moving animals to cleaned & disinfected finishing facilities", "continuous flushing of gutters" and "having a toilet on the farm". "No contact with other domestic animals (except pigs)", "drive-through tub for disinfection at farm entrance" and "presence of quarantine for introduction of animals" were identified as effective measures against HEV. Knowledge about factors affecting SAL and HEV occurrence in the pig production chain is incomplete given the large number and complexity of the interrelationships. In a second round of review, additional literature on pathogenic *E. coli* is considered.

In each of 9 European countries, about 30 pig farms were surveyed on the application of almost 60 biosecurity measures. Different production stages (birth to fattening) were considered. The results are compared with prevalence data collected in parallel. Data collection and sample analyses are still ongoing. As far as possible, first descriptive results will be shown in the presentation.

In an expert survey 57 biosecurity measures were evaluated with regard to their relevance for the control of SAL and HEV. For this purpose, 46 experts from 11 European countries were interviewed, including veterinarians, scientists, consultants and members of regulatory authorities. The experts rated the relevance of eight biosecurity categories (other animals, cleaning & disinfection, equipment, feed/water/litter, humans, mixing of pigs, purchasing, transport) and the relevance of 4 to 10 measures in each category. They ranked the relevance of the categories for both pathogens similarly. "Cleaning & disinfection" and "mixing of pigs" were considered most important. The experts' answers for HEV varied more, while the answers for SAL were mostly more consistent. Measures on contamination-free and protected storage of water and feed were considered relevant for HEV and SAL.

Furthermore, individual biosecurity measures (e.g. disinfection) are investigated and pathogen transmission including economic aspects are modelled. All effective measures are compiled in a catalogue. The aim is to develop a benchmarking system on biosecurity practices, a support tool for farmers and veterinarians, and information material for vocational schools. Results are planned to be discussed with experts at an online workshop (in December 2021) and a face-to-face workshop (May 2022 in the ESPHM pre-programme). The workshops are open to all interested parties.

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